

A Details of Instance Generation

A.1 TSPTW Instance Generation

In TSPTW, following the previous work of Bi et al. [1], each instance includes a depot node and $n - 1$ customer nodes. Node coordinates (x_i, y_i) are sampled from a uniform distribution $U[0, 100]$ within a square. Instances are generated across three difficulty levels to allow a complete evaluation of the performance of the solver. After generating the instances, all coordinates and time windows are normalized to $[0, 1]$ using the scaling factor $\rho = 100$.

Easy and medium TSPTW The difficulty is primarily controlled through the time window parameters. For each customer node i , the lower bound of the time window l_i is sampled from $U[0, T_N]$, where $T_N = 55N$ is an expected distance parameter dependent on the number of nodes N . Time window width w_i is sampled from $U[a, b] \cdot T_N$, with $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.75$ for easy instances and $a = 0.1$, $b = 0.2$ for medium instances. The upper bound is then generated based on l_i , where $u_i = l_i + w_i$.

Hard TSPTW In hard TSPTW, a random feasible tour τ is first generated, and time windows are constructed around arrival times within this tour. Specifically, for each node in the random tour τ , its time window is centered on the cumulative travel distance ψ_i up to step i . The lower bound of the time window l_i is sampled from $U[\psi_i - \eta, \psi_i]$ and the upper bound of the time window u_i is sampled from $U[\psi_i, \psi_i + \eta]$, where $\eta = 50$ controls the width of the time window. The upper bound of the depot is adjusted to $u_0 = \max_{i \in [1, n-1]} (u_i + \|v_i - v_0\|_2)$.

A.2 TSPDL Instance Generation

In TSPDL instances, given a percentage $\sigma\%$, the depot is assigned a demand $\delta_0 = 0$, while each port node receives a demand $\delta_i = 1$. $\lfloor N \times \sigma\% \rfloor$ nodes are randomly selected and assigned restricting draft limits from the range $[\delta_i, \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \delta_i]$, while the remaining nodes receive non-restricting draft limits equal to the total demand $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \delta_i$. Instance feasibility is verified using a sufficient and necessary condition: if nodes are ordered in ascending order of draft limits, the instance admits a feasible solution if and only if this ordering is feasible. If the condition is not satisfied, the instance is regenerated. The difficulty is controlled by $\sigma\%$, with $\sigma = 75$ used for medium instances and $\sigma = 90$ for hard instances, where a higher percentage creates more challenging instances by increasing the number of nodes with restricting draft limits.

B Network Architecture of FRDP

The network architectures of FRDP employ an encoder-decoder framework inherited from POMO [3], enhanced with specialized components for constraint handling.

B.1 Encoder

The encoder transforms static problem features into node embeddings through L successive attention layers. The initial node embeddings $h^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$ are generated by projecting static features into the embedding space. Specifically, $h_i^{(0)} = W_h[x_i, y_i, f_i]$, where (x_i, y_i) denotes coordinates, $f_i = (l_i, u_i)$ represents time windows in TSPTW and $f_i = (\delta_i, d_i)$ represents demands and draft limits in TSPDL. Adopting the same encoder as previous work [2, 3], the encoder employs L layers, where each layer updates the node embeddings with multi-head attention, feed forward network and normalization.

B.2 Decoder

The decoder architecture follows an autoregressive framework augmented with preventative infeasibility (PI) mask [1]. At each decoding step t , the decoder receives all node embedding h_i , the current node embedding h^t , dynamic state features s^t (current time for TSPTW and load for TSPDL) and the latent embedding z as inputs. The query (q), key (k) and value (v) are then computed as:

$$q^m = W_q^m[h^t + z, s^t], \quad k_i^m = W_k^m h_i, \quad v_i^m = W_v^m h_i \quad (1)$$

where W_q^m , W_k^m and W_v^m are learnable projection matrices of the m_{th} ($m \in [1, M]$) attention head. The latent embedding z is sampled from the Gaussian distribution $\{N(0, \frac{1}{d})\}^d$, where d is the dimension of the embedding. The context embedding h_c is then computed using multi-head cross-attention:

$$c^b = \sum_{i=0}^n \text{Softmax}\left(\frac{(q^m)^T k_i^m}{\sqrt{d}}\right) v_i^m \quad (2)$$

$$h_c = W_o[c^0, c^1, \dots, c^M]$$

where W_o is a linear layer to manage the output of each head. Finally, the logits for node selection are computed and transformed into probabilities using a single-head attention layer:

$$p_i = \text{Softmax}\left(C \tanh\left(\frac{h_c^T h_i}{\sqrt{d}} + \mathcal{M}\right)\right) \quad (3)$$

where C is a clipping constant and $\mathcal{M} \in \{0, -\infty\}^n$ is the PI mask vector preventing selection of invalid nodes. This architecture effectively combines static problem features, dynamic state information, and search history to generate feasible solutions for complex constrained routing problem variants.

C Setting of the scaling factor β in feasibility-guided reward

During training, as shown in Eq. (??), the best feasible solution receives its reward value $(R(\tau_i) - b)$, while the rewards of all other solutions are multiplied by

Table 1: Results on hard TSPTW ($n = 50$) with different β during training

β	Inf.	Obj.	Gap
0.2	2.30%	25.69	0.26%
0.05	1.74%	25.66	0.20%
0.02(Ours)	0.43%	25.64	0.13%
0.005	1.35%	25.64	0.11%

Table 2: Results on distribution of latent embedding on hard difficulty level

Distribution	TSPTW($n = 50$)		TSPDL($n = 50$)	
	Inf.	Gap	Inf.	Gap
Gaussian	0.43%	0.13%	0.00%	2.67%
Uniform	1.07%	0.14%	0.69%	2.64%

β ($\beta \times (R(\tau_i) - b)$). This reward mechanism is functionally equivalent to scaling the reward of the best solution by a factor of $\frac{1}{\beta}$. That is, the scaling factor β modulates the importance of the best feasible solution relative to other solutions within the reward, balancing exploitation and exploration during training. With the setting of β to a small but nonzero value, the algorithm is expected to strongly prioritize learning from the best feasible solution to promote exploitation, while maintaining a small but useful exploration ability by learning from other solutions.

Since we expect to promote the exploitation ability of the algorithm, β is set to 0.2, 0.05, 0.02, and 0.005, corresponding to the best feasible solution reward scaling factors of $5\times$, $20\times$, $50\times$, and $200\times$, respectively. As shown in Table 1, $\beta = 0.02$ demonstrated the best performance on hard TSPTW, achieving the lowest infeasibility rate (0.43%) while maintaining an optimal gap of 0.13%. Hence, $\beta = 0.02$ is selected in experiments on TSPTW and TSPDL.

D Analysis of the distribution of latent embeddings

We study the impact of samples drawn from different distributions in latent embedding. As shown in Table 2, in both hard TSPTW and hard TSPDL tasks, the infeasibility rate of solutions generated from Gaussian distributed latent embeddings is consistently lower than that from uniformly distributed samples. Specifically, the infeasibility rate for Gaussian sampling is 0.43% in TSPTW and 0.00% in TSPDL, while uniform sampling results in 1.07% in TSPTW and 0.69% in TSPDL. While the optimal gaps between the two distributions remain comparable, the uniform distribution achieves marginally smaller gaps in the TSPDL task. This suggests that the latent distribution shape significantly

Table 3: Performance on the TSPTW benchmark.

Instance	Opt.	PIP		PIP-D		FRDP		Instance	Opt.	PIP		PIP-D		FRDP	
		Obj.	Gap	Obj.	Gap	Obj.	Gap			Obj.	Gap	Obj.	Gap	Obj.	Gap
n20w20.001	378	389	2.91%	389	2.91%	391	3.44%	n40w40.003	474	496	4.64%	497	4.85%	489	3.16%
n20w20.002	286	292	2.10%	292	2.10%	292	2.10%	n40w40.004	452	/	/	/	/	/	/
n20w20.003	394	/	/	/	/	/	/	n40w40.005	453	470	3.75%	471	3.97%	470	3.75%
n20w20.004	396	405	2.27%	405	2.27%	405	2.27%	n40w60.001	494	/	/	525	6.28%	521	5.47%
n20w20.005	352	360	2.27%	360	2.27%	362	2.84%	n40w60.002	470	/	/	502	6.81%	500	6.38%
n20w40.001	254	276	8.66%	279	9.84%	276	8.66%	n40w60.003	408	/	/	/	/	438	7.35%
n20w40.002	333	347	4.20%	339	1.80%	341	2.40%	n40w60.004	382	406	6.28%	420	9.95%	398	4.19%
n20w40.003	317	332	4.73%	332	4.73%	332	4.73%	n40w60.005	328	342	4.27%	344	4.88%	342	4.27%
n20w40.004	388	401	3.35%	401	3.35%	396	2.06%	n40w80.001	395	407	3.04%	407	3.04%	409	3.54%
n20w40.005	288	294	2.08%	302	4.86%	296	2.78%	n40w80.002	431	448	3.94%	452	4.87%	448	3.94%
n20w60.001	335	349	4.18%	353	5.37%	345	2.98%	n40w80.003	412	444	7.77%	454	10.19%	438	6.31%
n20w60.002	244	252	3.28%	260	6.56%	253	3.69%	n40w80.004	417	430	3.12%	435	4.32%	436	4.56%
n20w60.003	352	358	1.70%	358	1.70%	358	1.70%	n40w80.005	344	362	5.23%	379	10.17%	360	4.65%
n20w60.004	280	298	6.43%	289	3.21%	287	2.50%	n60w80.001	458	/	/	/	/	496	8.30%
n20w60.005	338	385	13.91%	361	6.80%	353	4.44%	n60w80.002	498	540	8.43%	548	10.04%	555	11.45%
n20w80.001	329	347	5.47%	347	5.47%	346	5.17%	n60w80.003	550	635	15.45%	646	17.45%	594	8.00%
n20w80.002	338	347	2.66%	360	6.51%	348	2.96%	n60w80.004	566	611	7.95%	632	11.66%	612	8.13%
n20w80.003	320	328	2.50%	328	2.50%	330	3.13%	n60w80.005	468	535	14.32%	/	/	507	8.33%
n20w80.004	304	341	12.17%	339	11.51%	338	11.18%	n80w60.001	554	582	5.05%	/	/	592	6.86%
n20w80.005	264	302	14.39%	302	14.39%	300	13.63%	n80w60.002	633	678	7.11%	/	/	676	6.79%
n40w20.001	500	/	/	/	/	/	/	n80w60.004	619	678	9.53%	/	/	664	7.27%
n40w20.002	552	/	/	610	10.51%	574	3.99%	n80w60.005	575	/	/	/	/	639	11.13%
n40w20.003	478	/	/	507	6.07%	/	/	n80w80.001	624	/	/	/	/	665	6.57%
n40w20.004	404	419	3.71%	418	3.47%	420	3.96%	n80w80.002	592	624	5.41%	638	7.77%	625	5.57%
n40w20.005	499	/	/	/	/	/	/	n80w80.003	589	648	10.02%	674	14.43%	637	8.15%
n40w40.001	465	/	/	/	/	487	4.73%	n80w80.004	594	674	13.47%	676	13.80%	643	8.25%
n40w40.002	461	485	5.21%	483	4.77%	482	4.56%	n80w80.005	570	627	10.00%	/	/	614	7.72%
Average Gap			5.2%		5.3%		4.34%	Average Gap			7.44%		8.50%		6.54%
Infeasible%			22.2%		14.8%		14.8%	Infeasible%			25.93%		37.04%		3.70%

influences constraint satisfaction capabilities, with Gaussian sampling favoring feasibility at the cost of slight suboptimality.

E Experiment on TSPTW Benchmark

We conducted experiments on the TSPTW benchmark datasets and compared our method with PIP and PIP-D. Table 3 presents our experimental results. The results demonstrate that FRDP achieves competitive performance in both solution feasibility and optimality gap. Specifically, our approach outperforms existing methods across diverse benchmark instances, particularly in scenarios with the increased number of nodes.

References

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